

Material Rationale for Whole Building Design

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Abstract

Whole building design is an integrated approach to building design that considers all aspects of a building's life cycle, including energy and resource use, environmental impacts, and occupant health and well-being. This paper explores the concept of whole building design and its role in achieving sustainable buildings. Material selection plays a crucial role in achieving sustainable buildings, as the use of environmentally friendly materials can reduce the building's environmental impact and improve indoor air quality. Additionally, incorporating passive design strategies such as natural ventilation and daylighting can reduce energy consumption and improve occupant comfort. Effective communication and collaboration among all stakeholders are critical to the success of whole building design, as is the implementation of sustainable design principles throughout the project's lifecycle.

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Material Rationale for Whole Building Design

This paper will discuss the selection process, preparation, and installation of exterior metal doors, stucco, and laminated veneer lumber (LVL) in section one's analysis of whole building design. In section two, the rationale for selection and the practical and technical considerations involved in the preparation, placement, and installation of concrete, steel, and stone masonry are examined.

Whole Building Design

Design objectives in the *Whole Building Design Guide* by National Institute of Building Sciences [NIBS] (2021) include a variety of characteristics that, when taken as a whole, contribute to a successful construction project. These objectives that govern the selection of building materials will be referenced throughout this paper and include accessibility, aesthetics, cost-effectiveness, functionality, productivity, security, and sustainability (NIBS, 2021). In section one, those objectives as well as the preparation and installation considerations are examined in regard to exterior metal doors, stucco, and LVL beams.

Exterior Metal Doors

Material Selection

Exterior metal doors are selected for many new construction projects because they fulfill two specific design objectives: security and productivity, which are interrelated. Security characteristics of metal doors stem from the manner in which they are manufactured and the physical characteristics of the doors. The security design objective is fulfilled because the doors provide physical protection for building occupants. According to NIBS (2021), the productive design characteristics include building elements that pertain to occupants' well-being, which

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includes both physical and psychological comfort. The security afforded by exterior metal doors is physically protective and psychologically comforting.

Exterior metal doors are common in all types of new construction for every industry, including single-family and multi-family residential, industrial, healthcare, educational, and government buildings. While the material and labor associated with metal doors is higher than their fiberglass alternative, Doose (2014) says that they are stronger than traditional wood or fiberglass options and they reduce shrinking, swelling, and warping and resist fire and cracking. And because they are the stronger option compared to other alternative materials, they inherently increase the security of the occupants and assets inside a building. When security is a main concern, steel doors tend to be the best selection (Doose, 2014). Particularly in residential construction, physical security is just as important as the psychological comfort of living in a secure home that is afforded by this material.

Preparation

Preparation for the installation of exterior metal doors starts at the rough opening. Before installation begins, the size of the rough opening must be confirmed to match the design of the frame per the drawings (Steel Door Institute, 2009). Next, the hardware schedule must be checked to verify that the appropriate hinge size, strike type, and closer have been provided by the supplier. Since the floor finish affects how the door will be installed, the installer must verify whether the finished floor will be concrete, carpet, tile, or wood, and then adjust the frame to match that material thickness (Steel Door Institute, 2009). After this information has been verified and the frame has been adjusted, the door is ready to be installed.

Proper supplier selection prior installation can keep costs down make for a more sustainable installation. According to Lee (2021), locally sourced materials have reduced travel

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costs and therefore a lower carbon footprint. Purchasing from local suppliers or local manufacturers can have a positive impact to environmental considerations at a reduced cost.

Installation

When the frame has been placed inside of the rough opening, it must be plumbed with a framing square or magnetic level and squared, shimming where necessary to make it level (Steel Door Institute, 2009). At the bottom of the frame, a wood spreader is placed to keep the frame square during. Depending on whether the walls are masonry or wood, either anchor bolts are installed or anchor holes are predrilled. The hinges are then installed, the door hung, and a proper, even clearance between the door and frame are verified and adjusted if necessary to ensure that the door opens and closes properly (Steel Door Institute, 2021).

According to The University of Lethbridge (2021), safety concerns during the installation of metal doors include eye injuries and lifting hazards. Standard personal protection equipment (PPE), such as safety glasses and gloves, should be worn during the installation, and proper lifting techniques used to avoid injuries. When the door is being hung, two workers should be present, with one securing the door from falling while the other secures the hinges (University of Lethbridge, 2021).

Stucco

Material Selection

Stucco siding is a masonry plaster applied to exterior surfaces (Taylor & Vila, 2017). The material itself consists of cement, water, and sand and is typically applied to a wire lath with a hand trowel. According to Taylor and Vila (2017), a one-inch-thick coating of stucco provides a one-hour firewall rating, which meets the design objective for safety. This is a particularly attractive quality in material selection for multi-family buildings or homes which are in close

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proximity to each other, since stucco resists the spreading of flames.

The functional design objective refers to material performance and durability (NIBS, 2021). According to Holmes (2008), modern stucco with an acrylic-polymer, which expands and contracts with weather, keeps cracks to a minimum and can last up to 50 years before needing to be repaired. Stucco also breathes, which means that even though it can become saturated and allow moisture to penetrate through to the house wrap, it will also dry out. This is in contrast to other so-called waterproof products in which water may enter through areas like improperly sealed windows and have no method of escaping, leading to additional problems.

Preparation

The preparation process for the installation of stucco depends on the base on which it is to be installed. For example, stucco applied to a masonry wall generally only needs to be pre-wetted before applying the base coat (*Stucco Installation Standards*, 2019). Stucco applied to wood walls and ceilings requires a layer of oriented strand board (OSB) sheathing with a weather-barrier covering onto which a wire lath is attached (Vandervort, 2018). Once the masonry wall is pre-wetted or the wire lath is attached and the first base coat is mixed, stucco is ready to be installed.

When sustainability is a concern, certain stucco products can contribute to Leadership in Energy Environmental Design (LEED) credits. For example, Quikrete Lightweight FRS is blended with recycled polystyrene beads and weighs 35% less than traditional stucco (*QUIKRETE® Launches Industry's Lightest, Most Sustainable Stucco*, 2018). Lighter weight also means lower transport costs and material on site that is easier to stage and move.

Installation

Typically, stucco is applied while wet in three coats. According to Vandervort (2018), the

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first layer is the base layer, or scratch coat; followed by a second layer, called a brown coat; then the final finish coat. After the first coat is applied, the author notes that a notched trowel is used to scratch the surface with horizontal grooves, adding a texture to which the brown coat can adhere. The brown coat is applied a day or two after the scratch coat and the final coat is applied only after the brown coat has had one or two weeks to cure (Vandervort, 2018). While the first two coats can be troweled or sprayed onto the lath or masonry, the final coat is hand-troweled and textured.

Because stucco is installed on exterior walls that can be of any height, one of the main safety considerations in the installation process is fall hazards. According to the U.S. Department of Labor (2016), avoidable falls account for almost 40% of construction deaths. Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) standards dictate that fall protection must be used on activities six feet or more above the next lower level and ten feet or more on scaffolding (U.S. Department of Labor, 2016). When installing stucco from scaffolding, that means the worker should use tie offs as they ascend vertically.

Laminated Veneer Lumber

Material Selection

LVL beams fulfill a number of design objectives. Because they are structural components that can be manufactured to span almost any length, their use allows designers to create large open spaces without the need for columns. Selection of LVL in this kind of design fulfills the aesthetics design objective. Compared to solid lumber, LVL is a more sustainable building material, which is another reason for choosing to build with this material. Sustainability as defined by NIBS (2021) in the *Whole Building Design Guide* “pertains to environmental performance of building elements” (Sustainability section). However, the United States

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Environmental Protection Agency [EPA] (2016) elaborates further on green building by including the environmental effects of waste and the consumption of natural resources as impacted by the built environment. Since LVL beams are manufactured with veneers from less-valuable fast-growth trees whose wood is otherwise too weak for structural components and from which wood can be harvested every six to nine years as opposed to the 60 to 80 years for a hardwood like Oak, they are more sustainable than a solid wood alternative (Allen & Iano, 2014; Franklin, 2019).

Preparation

A main consideration in the preparation of LVL material is in proper on-site storage. When lumber packs are delivered, a building is usually in masonry. If it comes too soon while a building is still in slab or if there are construction delays, lumber material can be damaged if improperly stored. According to LP Building Products (2014b), LVL beams should be stored on a hard, level, dry surface on top of 2x4 spacers to prevent contact with the ground. The material should be maintained in a protective weather-resistant wrap, stacked no higher than ten feet, with each bundle separated by a 2x4 spacer no more than ten feet apart (see Figure 1) (LP Building Products, 2014b).

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Figure 1. Properly storing LVL material on-site involves the use of 2x4 wood spacers, weather-resistant wrap, and the avoidance of direct contact with the ground, which should be a hard, level, dry surface. Adapted from [Graphic showing proper LVL bundle storage] by LP Building Products, 2014a, *LP SolidStart LVL Technical Guide (2900Fb-2.0E)*, p. 16. Copyright 2014 by Louisiana-Pacific Corporation.

Since LVL beams are made with fibers from fast-growth trees, they are inherently more sustainable than sawn lumber. In order for LVL to contribute points to LEED certification, the products used must be certified by the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) (U.S. Green Building Council, 2008). The FSC certifies products that come from responsibly managed forests and requires each company involved in the chain of custody to be certified (Forest Stewardship Council [FSC], 2021). The intent of this requirement for LEED certification is to encourage environmentally responsible forest management, which includes replacing long-cycle renewables, like oak, with the rapidly renewable materials, like poplar, that are used in manufacturing engineered wood.

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Installation

Installation methods for LVL beams vary depending on whether the LVL is designed to support the ceiling or floor and whether the beams will be attached to masonry or wood. In the case of masonry attachments, LVL should not come into direct contact with concrete (LP Building Products, 2014b). Instead, metal masonry connectors are used which are screwed into the masonry using Tapcon screws or anchor bolts. These connectors provide a ledge for the LVL beam to sit into. When attached to wood framing, metal fasteners are also used. The beams are nailed into the fasteners, creating a secure connection. Depending on the span and type of construction, temporary supports may need to be erected to support the beam until it is connected and attached to all joists.

Principles of Construction Materials

The principles of construction materials examined are in regard to the practical suitability of the material; the material's performance or appropriateness in a variety of climates; the economics of procurement, installation, and performance; sustainability benefits or concerns; and safety considerations of performance and installation. Additionally, the main considerations in the preparation, placement, and installation are analyzed. The materials examined are concrete, with an emphasis on foundations; steel, with a focus on structural steel; and stone masonry, specifically building stones as opposed to stone veneer.

Concrete

Practical Suitability

To create a strong foundation for building vertically, concrete is the best material choice. Concrete, and particularly reinforced concrete, is a suitable material for foundation construction due to its compressive strength, durability, and fire resistance (Allen & Iano, 2014). It is a

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practical material because the four ingredients used to create it, portland cement, lime, a fine aggregate, and water, can be made from a variety of local materials in almost any region. For example, portland cement can be made from a combination of ingredients such as limestone, shells, chalk, marble, clay, sand, iron ore, and blast furnace slag (*How Cement Is Made*, 2019). Lime can be made from ingredients such as crushed shell, limestone, marble, or marl (Allen & Iano, 2014). The fine aggregate used can be sand; industrial waste such as steel or copper slag, coal bottom ash, or foundry sand; or agricultural waste such as oyster shell, rice husk ash, or tobacco waste, depending on local availability (Dash et al., 2016; Prusty et al., 2016). The final component is water, also a practical ingredient. These ingredients can be adjusted and substituted depending on local availability.

Climate

Concrete is an appropriate material choice for construction in any climate. Because of concrete's water resistance properties, it is an ideal building material for use in submerged applications like dams and canals, and for footers and slabs in waterfront structures (*Concrete in Construction: Uses, Advantages, and Types*, 2020). Concrete is a preferable material in seismic zones, since its ability to absorb vibration makes it resistant to earthquakes (*The Benefits of Concrete*, 2021). Once concrete has set, it is not affected by the temperature fluctuations that cause thermal expansion and contraction the way wood is, making it ideal for hot and cold climates alike. While the climate can affect hydration during the curing process, a number of mitigation techniques are available to offset effects from air temperature, such as chemical admixtures or the use of ice or hot water in the mixing process.

Economy

The economic benefits of concrete include the improved energy efficiency of the

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constructed building and the stability of pricing. Concrete buildings are more energy efficient than wood or steel because of their ability to store and release heat caused by solar radiation during the winter and to be cooled at night and release coolness into the building's interior in the summer months (Jacobs, 2007). This process, called thermal mass, results in lower energy costs associated with HVAC systems.

Concrete does not have the lowest upfront cost as a building material, but considerations such as cost savings as a result of concrete's high thermal mass factor into the economics of material selection over the life of a building. And because concrete pricing is less volatile than lumber and steel, forecasting costs in the design phase is more predictable and accurate. For example, throughout 2020 and 2021, as a result of production, supply chain, and labor issues combined with increased demand, building materials saw historically high price increases. In November of 2021, Economist Logan wrote about then-current year-to-date price increases for construction materials, noting that steel mill products increased 108.6% and softwood lumber 80%. In this same period, ready-mix concrete increased 4.8%. (Logan, 2021).

Sustainability

Concrete has many sustainable characteristics, such as durability, energy efficiency, and the ability to incorporate recycled waste ingredients in its mix. Conventionally built masonry and wood buildings have a life cycle of approximately 120 years before needing major repairs, while steel buildings have an expected lifespan of 52 years and require expensive renovation to maintain, often exceeding the cost of original construction (Rybczynski, 2015). The dean at Yale, Stern (n.d., as cited in Rybczynski, 2015), said in regard to the repair of campus buildings built in the 1960s which are considered architectural masterpieces, that the buildings "cost pennies to build and millions to renovate" (para. 1), such as Louis Kahn's art gallery, a

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modernist steel and glass building.

One of the most unique sustainability characteristics of concrete involves the wide variety of waste products that can be substituted in the ingredient mixture, resulting in the ability to recycle sometimes-hazardous waste while reducing the demand for raw materials. As mentioned above, a variety of industrial and agriculture waste products can be substituted for the natural sand fine aggregate in the cement mixture. Additionally, coarse aggregate, which gives concrete volume, can be replaced by a very wide variety of waste materials. The materials that can be recycled into concrete include plastic waste, glass, polystyrene, vehicle tires, and e-waste, such as televisions, laptops, and compact discs (Mahajan, 2021).

Safety

As previously mentioned, concrete safety features include its resistance to high wind loads and seismic activity. Concrete also has high resistance to fire. In fact, concrete is used in Type 1 buildings, the International Building Code's (IBC) highest fire resistance level, and is classified as class A1 material by the European Commission in European building standards, meaning it has the highest classification for fire resistance (Mineral Products Association, 2021). In terms of fire safety, concrete is one of the best choices as a building material.

Practical and Technical Considerations

Preparation.

Portland cement, lime, fine aggregate, and water are typically mixed in transit from the concrete plant and delivered to the job site in a plastic state. For slab pours, underground utilities and piping would have already been trenched and placed, formboards would have been set up, and rebar already in position prior to concrete delivery. Depending on the weather, the ground may be pre-wetted to cool it down in hot climates or admixtures may have been added to the

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concrete mixture to speed up hydration in colder climates (Allen & Iano, 2014). Typically, after water has been added and the hydration process has begun, there is a 90-minute window to pour the concrete.

Placement and Installation.

Concrete mixing trucks deliver plastic concrete to the job site and it is poured into place with a boom pump. It is spread by workers using shovels until it is at the desired level (Allen & Iano, 2014). Air pockets are then eliminated by using vibrators to agitate the concrete. The surface, still plastic, is flattened by hand using bull floats. Between four and six hours after the pour the concrete can be finished. This may involve using a trowel by hand, a rotary power trowel, a stiff push broom, or stamps (Allen & Iano, 2014). It is then left to cure for at least 28 days to harden and reach its full compressive strength.

In extreme weather, additional precautions may be taken to ensure the hydration process occurs without rapid evaporation of water or the halting of hydration due to freezing air temperatures. These mitigation techniques include protecting the slab from the sun with a shade, setting up misting machines to keep the slab surface cool, or covering a slab with an insulating blanket in cold weather.

Steel

Practical Suitability

Even though structural steel may outperform wood in terms of fire resistance and strength-to-weight ratio, it is not a practical material for residential construction due to the added cost and time for installation. However, in commercial applications, particularly in modernist projects and tall buildings, structural steel affords designers the freedom to build large, open spaces, include a variety of angles in their design, and build with almost no limit to height

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(Chahine, 2020). It is also a practical material for multi-family and office buildings over four stories, as its fire resistance qualities add a layer of safety unmatched by wood, which is discussed below.

Climate

Buildings with structural steel frames are appropriate in any climate, as evidenced by landmark buildings in a variety of climates such as One World Trade Center in New York, US; Shun Hing Square Tower in Shenzhen, China; Taipei 101 Tower in Taiwan; Burj Khalifa in Dubai, UAE; and the Sydney Harbor Bridge in Sydney, Australia. However, structural steel members exposed to the elements, like those used in bridges and roadways, are susceptible to atmospheric corrosion, which causes a loss in thickness and compromised structural integrity (Jančula et al., 2021). Mitigation involves frequent monitoring and often costly maintenance.

Economy

In an impartial study commissioned by the British Constructional Steelwork Association and Tata Steel (2016, as cited in *Cost Comparison Study*, 2021), a typical office-building envelope made of steel was found to cost 15% less than a similar concrete building and 4% lower on a whole-building basis. When the schedule was taken into account, the same comparative study found that steel framing saved 12 weeks over concrete (*Cost Comparison Study*, 2021). With other steel products like metal roofs, their economic benefits lie in enhancing a building's energy efficiency and the product's durability. The Metal Roofing Alliance (n.d., as cited in Kazlov, 2015) says that a metal roof's reflective and radiant heat emissive properties can result in lower the cost of cooling a building up to 40% in the summer.

Sustainability

The process of manufacturing steel is highly pollutive and damaging to the environment.

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According to Allen and Iano (2014), raw materials are used that are quarried or mined from the earth, which often pollutes streams and rivers. The authors also say that the production of one ton of steel by the basic oxygen process results in 4,550 pounds of gaseous emissions as well as 650 pounds of industrial waste, including slag and dust. Sustainability in steel material comes from the incorporation of recycled ingredients. Most steel in North America is made from 90% recycled steel scrap and is manufactured using the electric arc furnace process, which uses one-third the energy of steel made from iron ore (Allen & Iano, 2014). Besides the incorporation of recycled material in the manufacturing process, steel is also made more sustainable by the high rate at which it is recycled. According to Allen and Iano (2014), 95 percent of all structural steel used in North America is eventually recycled or reused.

Safety

Steel is very strong and, being non-combustible, is resistant to fire. Steel is unique in that it is the only fire-resistant construction material to have both useful tensile strength and compressive strength (Allen & Iano, 2014). In fact, it can have as much as 43 times the compressive strength of unreinforced concrete, which has no tensile strength (Allen & Iano, 2014). Large, safe buildings that last many years are possible because of the properties of structural steel. And, like concrete, steel is used in Type 1 construction, meaning that it is non-combustible and fire-resistant.

Safety considerations with structural steel involve the occupational risk during the installation process. Like stucco, as mentioned in section one, one of the main concerns with structural steel installation is fall protection, which is mandated by OSHA, since steel is often used in the construction of tall buildings. Figure 2 shows an image during the construction of Rockefeller Center in New York, 39 years prior to the founding of OSHA. Of note is that none of

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the workers are wearing PPE or using any form of fall protection, despite the fact that they are 850 feet in the air.

Figure 2. Ironworkers at 850 feet above Rockefeller Center in New York City with no fall protection or PPE. From *Lunch Atop a Skyscraper*, by Ebbets, C., 1932, The New York Times (https://static01.nyt.com/images/2012/11/11/arts/11LUNCH1_SPAN/11LUNCH1_SPAN-jumbo.jpg).

Practical and Technical Considerations

Preparation.

Before any fabrication can begin on structural steel, detailed shop drawings must be approved by the designer. These drawings consist of precise dimensions, connection details, details for each steel member, and installation instructions (Allen & Iano, 2014). When the shop drawings have been approved or revised, cardboard templates are made to assist shop workers with proper placement during the fabrication process, which also includes cutting plates, angles, and connections to size (Allen & Iano, 2014). When the steel members arrive from the

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manufacturer, they are painted with a code identifying the member's location in relation to the shop drawings and the beams are prepared for transportation to the job site after connecting plates are welded and bolt holes are punched (Allen & Iano, 2014).

Placement and Installation.

Mobile cranes or fixed-tower cranes are used to lift steel members in place and are then bolted down by ironworkers (Allen & Iano, 2014). Before being welded to the baseplate, leveling nuts can adjust the steel member to ensure that it is plumb. After the initial columns are in place, beams and girders are lifted by cranes, bolted in place, adjusted for level, and welded (Allen & Iano, 2014).

Stone Masonry

Practical Suitability

Building stone is suitable for residential or commercial buildings because it can be procured locally, it has similar compressive strength to reinforced concrete, it is non-combustible, and does not require exterior finish material, like siding. It is not susceptible to temperature fluctuations, atmospheric corrosion, rot, or insect damage. However, because of the high upfront expense of stone, it will be impractical for many typical building projects such as standard residential homes and commercial retail (*Pros & Cons of Building a Stone House*, 2019).

Climate

Stone is notoriously difficult to insulate and has a high thermal mass compared to other structures. In hot climates, cool air will escape through the stone walls and heat will escape in the winter without insulation. According to Garcia (n.d.), when a solid piece of stone is used on the exterior and interior walls, the building takes on the ambient temperature from outside. The

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author states that the best method of insulating is stone from the outside to prevent the negative impact of thermal mass, although that would mean covering the exterior walls and losing the stone aesthetic, which is usually the point of constructing with stone. While the material is durable in any climate, it can be challenging to heat and cool.

Economy

Stone is expensive to procure, expensive to transport, and requires skilled craftsmen to install. Because of the challenges with energy efficiency, there is a potential for additional costs in heating and cooling the building. For example, a typical concrete masonry unit (CMU) can be installed by a mason for approximately \$3 per square foot, while labor for stone workers is between \$20-\$30 per square foot, depending on skill level (Anderson, 2021). One economic characteristic of stone is durability. Stone buildings can last hundreds of years, which also makes them more sustainable.

Sustainability

The durability of stone is one of its greatest sustainability attributes. When wood or concrete buildings are being torn down after 50 or 60 years, stone buildings can remain in use for hundreds of years. For example, the Castel Sant'Angelo in Rome was constructed in 401 C.E. out of travertine, a type of limestone, and is still in use today as a functioning tourist attraction and museum (Bernard, 2021). And because stone masonry is finished, the use of volatile organic compounds like paint or other finish materials like siding is not necessary, eliminating the need for products that have their own negative environmental impacts (Allen & Iano, 2014).

Stone is a natural resource that is quarried from the earth, which is not a sustainable practice; and, up to 50% of quarried stone can become waste during fabrication (Allen & Iano, 2014). However, in some regions stone can be recycled. For example, in the copper mining town

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of Calumet, Michigan, basalt rock that was mined in pursuit of copper was saved for use as a building material. Among the many buildings constructed at the time using this material, in 1887 the offices of the Calumet & Hecla Mining Company were built using this recycled basalt stone, referred to as poor rock (National Park Service, 2021). In Figure 3, the brick trim is a veneer over poor rock and the darker basalt foundation is clearly evident.

Figure 3. Headquarters of the National Park Services in Calumet, Michigan, formerly the offices of the Calumet & Hecla Mining Company, constructed in 1887 of poor rock, reclaimed basalt stone that was mined in the pursuit of copper. From *Keweenaw NHP Headquarters* by NPS, n.d., U.S. National Park Service

(https://www.nps.gov/common/uploads/cropped_image/primary/581B2B65-AFA9-552A-6D92DC994FF36B42.jpg).

Safety

As mentioned above, stone has very high compressive and tensile strength, can resist high wind loads, and is non-combustible, making it a very safe material to construct with. Safety concerns related to stone are occupational rather than design-related. For example, stone masons

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are repetitively lifting and placing large slabs of stone, are exposed to loud noises from the stone-cutting saws, and are at risk for upper limb disorders from using vibrating hand tools (*Safety Risks Associated With Stonemasonry*, 2021). Some mitigation techniques for these issues include maintaining clear paths where stones will be moved on site, safety training and supervision in regard to moving stones, use of personal protection equipment (PPE) when cutting stone, including hearing protection, and the use of ergonomically-designed cutting tools (*Safety Risks Associated With Stonemasonry*, 2021).

Practical and Technical Considerations

Preparation.

Preparation of stone material begins at the quarry site, where the stone is hewn by hand, cut by machine, or blasted (Anupoju, 2021b). After the material is quarried, it is then transported to cutting sheds to be *dressed*, or cut into required sizes, which usually occurs at the quarry site to reduce initial transportation costs (Anupoju, 2021a). If laying stone on a concrete foundation, the concrete must be properly cured before installation can begin. Stone should be delivered to the site as close to the work area as possible and mortar mixed in preparation for the installation.

Installation.

There are a variety of methods of laying stone depending on the type of stone and the pattern. *Rubble masonry* uses unsquared stones that may be coursed or uncoursed and, because of the irregular sizes of the stones, require special attention by an experienced mason to choose each stone carefully for proper placement (Allen & Iano, 2014). If the stone pieces are too heavy to lift manually, they will be hoisted into place and trimmed manually with a hammer and chisel (Allen & Iano, 2014). Whether rubble masonry or coursed, square stones are laid, they are set in a mortar bed like concrete masonry, plumbed, and packed with mortar on each successive course

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(Better Homes & Gardens, 2021). As the mortar begins to set, the joints are finished with a concave jointer or other tool, depending on the finish design.

As mentioned above, part of the installation process includes the use of proper lifting technique and PPE to avoid occupational injuries. Keeping the job site clean is part of the construction process to avoid creating hazards for other trades. Stone dust can be damaging to the respiratory system, leading to asthma or chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) (Watson, 2020). Working in a ventilated area and sweeping the site with a wet push broom can help prevent other trade workers who might not be wearing dust masks from breathing in the harmful dust.

Conclusion

A variety of factors influence the selection of construction materials in the design process. Among them are budgetary concerns, aesthetics, durability, sustainability, safety, and performance. The intended use of the building is also factored along with these considerations when specifying material. On a construction project, the installation process really begins by preparing for installation. Preparation considerations include sourcing the material, field measuring, waiting for concrete to cure, submitting shop drawings for approval, and securing safe on-site material delivery and storage. Safety considerations are part of both the preparation and installation process, as the site conditions must be conducive to a safe installation and workers are responsible for safe practices, such as the proper use of fall protection and PPE. Sustainability is a very broad term that encompasses quantifying the energy used in manufacturing, environmental impacts of transportation, locally sourcing materials, inclusion of recycled materials, and longevity of the material. Fire safety considerations are also paramount in material selection. For Type 1 and Type 2 construction, non-combustible materials like steel,

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concrete, stone, stucco, and metal doors contribute to a building's fire rating. These principles of construction materials inform the material selection process by designers and builders.

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